

Investment Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics Using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around investment risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The research was conducted from 1995 to 2022, by searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Scopus, and WoS via the Perish/Harzing application, with the keyword "Investment Risk". Based on the search results, there were 280 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to investment risk is divided into 16 clusters and 116 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 9 main themes related to investment risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Investment Risk, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

INTRODUCTION

Risk management in banking has improved in line with developments in the financial industry as a whole. In recent years, banks have begun to understand the importance of risk management to maintain business stability and continuity. This can be seen from the existence of regulations from the Financial Services Authority (OJK) which regulate risk exposure management and effective corporate governance. Risks in the financial sector must be recognized and controlled by estimating the potential that may occur in the future, not after the risk has already occurred. Therefore, a methodology for modeling risks that may occur in the future is very important so that those making decisions can prepare strategies to overcome future risks. One of the risks that occur in the financial industry is investment risk. Investment risk management involves identifying, assessing, controlling and monitoring these risks over time to ensure that the bank remains stable and maintains its reputation.

In previous research, the development of investment risk in banking can be influenced by several factors, such as changes in interest rates, financial market fluctuations, changes in regulations, and macroeconomic conditions. Banks can also take proactive steps to reduce risk, such as diversifying investment portfolios or implementing technology to monitor risk in real-time. Banks must also ensure that their investments meet regulatory requirements and have a risk level that is appropriate to the bank's risk profile. Banks must also consider environmental and social implications in managing investment risks. This relates to the principles of social and environmental responsibility which are increasingly important for banking. Banks can manage investment risks by ensuring that their investments meet established environmental and social standards, such as ESG (environmental, social and governance) standards. This can help banks minimize risks and ensure that their investments have a positive impact on the environment and society. In managing investment risk, banks must also ensure that they have procedures and mechanisms to deal with emergency or crisis situations. This includes having backup plans and simulations to deal with worst-case scenarios. Banks must ensure that they have the resources and capabilities to overcome emergency situations and ensure the stability of their businesses. Therefore, banks must continue to adapt and update their risk management systems to ensure the stability and continuity of their business.

Based on the problems above, it is necessary to map investment risk management topics to identify, measure and control risks that will occur. This can fulfill the need for human resources

tasked with risk management to have knowledge, skills and work attitudes according to the bank's needs. So, the aim of this research is to map research topics around investment risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature review study to analyze, identify and review articles from indexed international journals and accredited national journals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Investment risk is the risk of loss that may occur as a result of an investment made by a bank. This can be caused by various factors, such as market fluctuations, economic changes, government policies, or internal factors such as management errors. In banking, investment risks are often related to products such as bonds, shares or other financial instruments which can cause losses for the bank and customers if not managed properly. Therefore, banks must carefully consider the risks of each investment they will make and ensure that they have mechanisms to address and manage these risks.

Bibliometric studies are a branch of science that analyzes and evaluates scientific publications and related information. It involves the use of statistical and informatics methodologies to assess the production, citation, and dissemination of knowledge in scientific literature. Bibliometric studies can be used to measure the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions and scientific fields, as well as to understand interactions and relationships between scientific fields and publications. It can also help in the identification and evaluation of trends and issues in the scientific literature. Some applications of bibliometric studies include citation network analysis, cluster analysis, and visibility analysis. Results from bibliometric studies can be used by researchers, government, and industry to understand developments and contributions in scientific fields and to determine future research directions.

VOSviewer is bibliometric software used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data. It allows users to visualize citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis data in the form of graphs and diagrams that are intuitive and easy to accept. VOSviewer can help researchers and analysts carry out citation network analysis, find relationships between scientific fields, and understand trends and issues in scientific literature. It also helps in determining future research directions and gaining insight into the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions, and scientific fields. VOSviewer has an easy-to-use user interface and can be used together with data coming from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. It allows users to visualize and analyze publication data effectively and efficiently.

Literature review is a process that includes identification, evaluation, and synthesis of results from previous research on a specific topic. It aims to provide an overview of trends, issues, and advances in related fields and assist in understanding how previous research influences future research developments and directions. Literature review studies are usually conducted as part of the research process to ensure that researchers understand the existing research environment and produce non-duplicative results. It also helps in determining problems and gaps in the existing literature and helps in the formulation of hypotheses and understanding of specific research areas. Literature review studies can be carried out by accessing scientific publication databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Researchers can also carry out manual searches through scientific journals and related books. Literature review studies must be carried out with a systematic and objective methodology to ensure that the results are accurate and valid.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is investment risk. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on investment risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Scopus, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keyword " Investment Risk " within the entire year period (1995 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics research based on literature review studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Investment Risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are 280 international and national journals based on the results of data collection from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 1995 to 2022. There are 70 journals Scopus indexed international. And there is 210 international and national journals indexed by Sinta around investment risk research.

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding Investment Risk by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
1995-1999	16	2005	3	2011	11	2017	8
2000	2	2006	4	2012	17	2018	19
2001	2	2007	1	2013	18	2019	9
2002	5	2008	11	2014	20	2020	14
2003	5	2009	10	2015	23	2021	26
2004	2	2010	17	2016	20	2022	17

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Investment Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are several things that need to be considered when knowing bibliometric results with software VOSviewer, namely: first, the software interface, namely the VOSviewer interface displays diagrams and graphs that visualize publication data. Users can open and explore these charts and graphs by clicking on specific items or zooming in on specific parts of the diagram. Second, visual components, namely several visual components that may appear in VOSviewer bibliometric results including nodes (representations of publications), lines (representations of citation relationships), and colors (representations of categories or topics). Third, citation network analysis, namely citation network analysis helps in determining relationships between publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. Larger nodes in the diagram represent more widely noted publications and relationships between nodes can help in understanding how publications are related. Fourth, cluster analysis, namely cluster analysis helps in determining relationships between topics or fields of science and understanding how publications are related to certain topics or fields of science. The colors in the diagram represent categories or topics and help in understanding how publications relate to different topics or fields

- Cluster 8, consists of 7 topic items, namely: asset management, bank trader, global standards, relationships, responsible investment, risk management frameworks, soft law standards.
- Cluster 9, consists of 6 topic items, namely: capital, clients, financial risk, firm value, good corporate governance, investment decisions.
- Cluster 10, consists of 6 topic items, namely: banks, sharia banks, Indonesia, risk, SBI, significant.
- Cluster 11, consists of 6 topic items, namely: credit risk management, development, investment, joint stock commercial bank, Kigali, Vietnam.
- Cluster 12 consists of 5 topic items, namely: banking firm, behavior, credit risk, organizational change, risk.
- Cluster 13, consists of 4 topic items, namely: bank credit risk, investment bank, London, risk aversion.
- Cluster 14 consists of 4 topic items, namely: bank capital, central bank, risk management, strategy.
- Cluster 15, consists of 3 topic items, namely: enterprise risk management, investment banking industry, var.
- Cluster 16, consists of 1 topic item, namely: European investment bank.

Mapping Literature Review regarding the Definition and Objectives of Investment Risk Management

First, the definition of Investment Risk. Investment risk in banking is the potential loss that may occur when deciding to invest in financial instruments offered by the bank. These risks may arise due to several factors, such as changes in economic conditions, changes in interest rates, fluctuations in currency values, or failure of beneficiaries to fulfill their obligations. Therefore, it is important for every investor to understand and consider investment risks before deciding to invest in certain banking products.

Second, the aim of Investment Risk management is to minimize potential losses that may occur from investment activities carried out by the bank. Some of the main objectives of investment risk management in banking include: (1) Preventing losses, namely investment risk management focuses on identifying, evaluating and controlling potential risks that may occur in bank investment activities; (2) Ensuring financial stability, namely by ensuring that investment risks taken by banks can be controlled and reduced, investment risk management helps ensure bank financial stability; (3) Maximizing profits, namely investment risk management also aims to help banks maximize profits obtained from investment activities; (4) Fulfilling regulations, namely in several countries, there are regulations governing investment risk management in banking, and the objectives of investment risk management also include meeting the requirements of these regulations; and (5) Increasing reputation, namely banks that have good investment risk management can build a positive reputation, which can help strengthen relationships with customers and increase market trust.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Investment Risk Supervision

Findings in this research topic include:

First, the authority and responsibility of the Board of Commissioners. Some of the main tasks of the Board of Commissioners in managing investment risk in banking include: (1) Ensuring that the bank has an effective risk management system to manage investment risk; (2) Ensure that the investment strategy taken by the bank is in accordance with the bank's financial objectives and plans; (3) ensuring that the bank provides accurate and timely reports on investment risks taken by the bank; (4) ensuring that the bank has a strong commitment to sound financial principles and makes investments in a manner that is consistent with these principles. In carrying out these tasks, the Board of Commissioners must work together with the Board of

Directors and the bank's risk department to ensure that the bank can manage investment risks effectively.

Second, the authority and responsibility of the Board of Directors. The Board of Directors in banking has important authority in managing investment risk. Some of their main tasks in this regard are as follows: (1) Determining an investment strategy that is in accordance with banking objectives and risk profiles, as well as the investment strategy chosen meets applicable regulations and has the potential for satisfactory returns; (2) Monitor investment risks periodically and take necessary actions to reduce discovered risks; (3) Approve certain investments recommended by the risk department or investment banking department, as well as investments that are approved to meet applicable regulations and are in accordance with the determined investment strategy; (4) Ensure that investments made by banks are carried out properly and in accordance with applicable regulations, as well as ensuring that investments meet security standards and monitoring investment performance periodically. In general, the Board of Directors has the primary responsibility for ensuring that investment risks in banking are managed well and comply with applicable regulations. They ensure that investments made by banks have the potential for satisfactory returns and do not pose unnecessary risks for banks.

Third, related to Human Resources/HR. Human resources (HR) are an important factor in determining investment risk in banking. Quality and competent human resources can help banks manage risks and ensure that business processes run efficiently. However, if human resources do not meet required standards, this can pose a risk to investment. Some examples of HR risks in banking include: (1) If a bank loses competent and experienced employees, this could pose a risk to the business and affect the bank's overall performance; (2) A high employee turnover rate can pose a risk for the bank, especially if the employees who leave have important information and skills; (3) If the bank does not have a good recruitment policy, this can create risks for the bank, such as hiring employees who do not meet the required standards; and (4) If the bank does not have enough employees to handle the volume of business, this could create risks for the bank and affect the quality of services provided. By paying attention to HR risks, banks can take steps to manage and reduce these risks, such as creating an attractive work environment, improving the quality of HR through training and career development, and ensuring that employee recruitment and retention policies meet the required standards.

Fourth, related to the Investment Risk Management Organization. The investment risk management organization in banking is part of the banking risk management system which is responsible for identifying, evaluating and managing investment risks faced by banks. The aim is to ensure that the bank has a good understanding of the investment risks it faces and ensure that these risks are managed effectively. The main functions of an investment risk management organization in banking include: (1) Establishing and implementing investment risk management procedures; (2) Monitoring and evaluating the bank's investment portfolio; (3) Analyze and monitor investment risks, such as market risk, credit risk, operational risk and liquidity risk; (4) Provide recommendations for strategies and actions to manage investment risks; and (5) Ensure that the bank meets the applicable regulations and regulatory standards for investment risk management. The investment risk management organization in banking works closely with other departments such as the finance department, accounting department, and audit department to ensure that the bank has an effective risk management system and meets industry standards.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Strategy, Risk Level, Policies, Procedures and Limits in Investment Risk Management

First, Investment Risk management strategy. Investment risk management in banking involves various steps and strategies to reduce or minimize potential losses that may occur in bank investment activities. The following are several investment risk management strategies in banking: (1) Portfolio diversification, namely a strategy that involves dividing investments into several different types of financial instruments, such as bonds, shares and real estate, so that the risk of loss can be divided and reduced; (2) Banks must carry out regular risk analysis to ensure that investments made meet accepted risk standards and meet the bank's financial objectives; (3)

Banks must monitor and evaluate investment performance regularly to ensure that the investment still meets acceptable risk objectives and standards; (4) Banks must limit the type and amount of investments made, especially in instruments that have high risk; (5) Banks must have an effective asset protection system to ensure that investments in the portfolio are protected from the risk of loss; and (6) Banks must ensure that they have sufficient liquidity to meet their obligations and maintain the bank's financial stability. An investment risk management strategy in banking is very important to ensure that the bank has a stable investment portfolio that produces satisfactory results, as well as minimizing the risk of possible losses.

Second, the level of risk to be taken (Risk Appetite) and risk tolerance (Risk Tolerance) in Investment Risk. Risk Appetite is the level of risk that banks or investors are willing to take in investing. This shows how much the party is prepared to take risks to achieve its goals. Usually, banks have a lower risk appetite because they have to consider reputation and applicable policies, as well as ensuring that their customers' funds are safe. Meanwhile, Risk Tolerance is the level of risk that can be accepted by banks or investors in investing. It shows how much risk is acceptable before it affects financial or investment goals. Typically, risk tolerance levels will vary depending on an individual's financial situation and investment goals. These two concepts are very important for banks and investors in determining investment strategies and making wise investment decisions. They must understand the level of risk they are able to bear and determine an investment portfolio that suits their risk appetite and risk tolerance.

Third, Investment Risk policy. Investment risk in banking is one of the risks that banks must consider when carrying out investment activities. In managing this risk, banks usually implement the following policies: (1) Portfolio Diversification, namely banks try to expand their investment reach by purchasing various types of investment instruments such as shares, bonds or deposits, so that risks can be distributed and not concentrated in one type of investment only; (2) Risk limitation, namely banks limit the amount of risk that can be taken by setting limits on buying or selling certain types of investments; (3) Monitoring and evaluation, namely banks regularly monitor and evaluate their investments to ensure that investments remain within safe limits and in accordance with established policies; (4) Risk analysis, namely the bank carries out an in-depth risk analysis before making an investment, to ensure that the investment has potential returns commensurate with the level of risk accepted; and (5) Asset protection, namely banks ensure that their investments are protected by using insurance products or purchasing products that have protection against certain risks. By implementing these policies, banks can manage their investment risks and ensure that these investments can generate profits for their shareholders and customers. However, even though these policies have been implemented, investment risks still exist and cannot be completely eliminated. Therefore, banks must continuously monitor and evaluate their investment risks and take necessary actions to address these risks if necessary.

Fourth, Investment Risk procedures. The investment risk process in banking is a series of stages carried out by banks to ensure that every investment made has a controlled level of risk and is in accordance with the bank's investment objectives. The following are several stages in the investment risk process in banking: (1) Risk identification, namely this stage involves identifying and evaluating risks that may occur in each investment. Risks that need to be identified include credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk and operational risk; (2) Risk evaluation, namely after the risk has been identified, the next stage is risk evaluation. In this stage, the bank will determine the level of risk accepted for each investment; (3) Risk monitoring and control, namely this stage involves continuous risk monitoring and control; (4) Risk documentation and reporting, namely banks must regularly record and report risks that occur in each investment; and (5) Risk analysis and strategic considerations, namely the final stage in the investment risk process is risk analysis and strategic considerations. By carrying out the investment risk process correctly, banks can ensure that the investments made have a controlled level of risk and are in line with the bank's investment objectives.

Fifth, Investment Risk limit. The investment risk limit procedure in banking involves several important stages and steps, such as: (1) Risk identification, namely the bank must identify the types of investment risks that may arise during the investment process, including market risk,

credit risk, liquidity risk, etc. other; (2) Determination of risk limits, namely after the investment risk is known, the bank must determine the appropriate risk limit for each type of risk; (3) Risk monitoring, namely after the risk limit is determined, the bank must monitor investment risk regularly. This ensures that the bank can monitor investment progress and make adjustments where necessary to ensure that investments remain within specified risk limits; (4) Adjustment of risk limits, namely banks must be willing to adjust investment risk limits if the situation changes. This ensures that the bank can take into account changes in the market and ensure that investments remain within appropriate risk limits; and (5) Procedure documentation, namely the bank must provide clear documentation regarding investment risk limit procedures. This ensures that the bank has clear evidence of the steps taken to limit investment risks. In general, investment risk limit procedures in banking ensure that banks limit potential losses that may occur during the investment process. These measures ensure that banks remain within appropriate risk limits and maintain financial stability over the long term.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Identification, Measurement, Monitoring, Control and Investment Risk Information Systems

First, identify investment risks. To identify investment risks in banking, here are several things that need to be considered: (1) Credit risk, namely the borrower being unable to repay the loan received from the bank, and can be reduced by carrying out due diligence and ensuring that the bank has appropriate credit policies and procedures. strong; (2) Interest rate risk, which is related to changes in interest rates; (3) Market risk, which is related to price changes on the financial market; (4) Operational risk, which is related to failure to manage bank operations effectively; (5) Regulatory risk, which is related to changes in government rules and regulations. Banks must ensure that they comply with all applicable regulatory requirements; (6) Reputation risk, which is related to the negative impact on the bank's image which can be caused by scandals, unethical business practices, or other problems. It is important to remember that each bank will have different risks, depending on factors such as type of business, scale of operations and financial position. Therefore, it is important for investors to do research and carry out due diligence before making any form of investment.

Second, measuring Investment Risk. Measuring investment risk in banking involves analysis and evaluation of potential losses that may be experienced by banks in making investments. There are several types of risk that need to be taken into account in measuring investment risk in banking, including: (1) Credit risk, namely risk related to the possibility of failure of the party receiving investment funds to repay the loan received; (2) Market risk, namely risk related to changes in the prices of investment instruments owned by banks, such as shares, bonds and money market instruments; (3) Operational risk, namely risk related to failure in implementing investment operations, such as administrative errors or ineffective management; and (4) Liquidity risk, namely risk related to the bank's ability to sell or buy back investment instruments when needed. To measure investment risk in banking, banks can use several techniques, such as sensitivity analysis, stress testing, and value-at-risk (VaR) analysis. The results of this risk measurement can then be used to make more informative and wise investment decisions.

Third, monitoring Investment Risk, namely:

- (1) Investment risk monitoring in banking is a process carried out by banks to monitor and measure investment risks that may occur in the bank's investment portfolio. This is done to ensure that the bank has a clear understanding of potential risks and ensures that the bank has effective risk management to address these risks.
- (2) Investment risk monitoring is carried out regularly and involves continuous evaluation of investments, monitoring changes in market and economic situations, and ensuring that bank investments meet applicable policy and regulatory standards.
- (3) Several types of investment risks that banks must consider include credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk and operational risk. Banks must identify these risks and ensure that they have appropriate risk management in place to address any possible risks.

- (4) In monitoring investment risk, banks must also ensure that bank investments have performance that meets set targets and that the bank's investment portfolio is balanced and diversified.

Fourth, controlling Investment Risk. Controlling investment risk in banking is very important to ensure the stability and continuity of bank business. The following are several ways that can be used to control investment risk in banking: (1) Portfolio diversification, namely by spreading investments across various types of instruments, banks can reduce the risk that a loss on one instrument will affect the entire portfolio; (2) Risk monitoring and analysis, namely banks must continue to monitor and analyze investment risks periodically to ensure that the investment is still in accordance with the accepted risk profile; (3) Risk Management Framework, namely the bank must have an adequate risk management framework to ensure that all risks related to investment can be recognized, assessed and controlled; (4) Limitation of Concentration Risk, namely banks must limit concentration risk by not considering large investments in one type of instrument or particular industry; (5) Financial management, namely banks must ensure that they have a strong and liquid financial position to ensure that they can maintain their position during periods of market volatility; and (6) Education and training, namely banks must provide education and training to staff to ensure that they understand investment risks and have the ability to control them.

Fifth, Investment Risk Management Information System/SIMRI, namely:

- (1) A system used to assist banks in managing and measuring investment risk. In banking, investment risk can come from various sources such as credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk and operational risk.
- (2) This system aims to ensure that banks have a good understanding of the investment risks they face, as well as having appropriate mechanisms to manage and measure these risks. SIMRI also helps banks identify and monitor investment risks over time, and make decisions based on the latest information and data.
- (3) SIMRI usually uses mathematical modeling methods and statistical analysis to measure investment risk and predict potential losses that may occur. This system also provides reports and analyzes that help banks make wise investment decisions.
- (4) In implementing SIMRI, banks must ensure that the data used in the system is accurate and up to date. Banks must also ensure that these systems are always updated and improved to meet regulatory changes and market developments.
- (5) In general, SIMRI helps banks manage investment risks effectively and ensures that banks have a good understanding of the risks they face. This is important to ensure banking financial stability and ensure that investors and banking customers are protected.

Sixth, the Internal Investment Risk Control System (Internal Investment Risk Control System), which is a system used by banks to monitor and manage the investment risks they face. This helps banks to ensure that their investments comply with banking policies and objectives, as well as meet regulatory requirements and industry standards. Some of the main tasks of this internal control system are: (1) Risk identification, namely identifying various types of investment risks faced by banks, such as market risk, credit risk, liquidity risk and operational risk; (2) Risk evaluation, namely assessing the level of risk associated with each investment and ensuring that the investment is in accordance with the banking risk tolerance; (3) Monitoring and Reporting, namely monitoring and reporting any changes in investment risk and ensuring that appropriate action is taken if necessary; (4) Policies and procedures, namely ensuring that banks have clear and tested policies and procedures for managing investment risks, and ensuring that these policies and procedures are followed consistently; (5) Training and education, namely providing training and education to banking staff on how to manage investment risks and ensuring that they understand how to carry out their duties correctly. The Investment Risk Internal Control System is very important for banks because it helps them to ensure that their investments are safe and well managed.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Determinants of Investment Risk

Determinants of investment risk in banking are factors that influence the risks associated with investment in the banking sector. These include factors such as general economic conditions, the quality of the bank's assets, interest rates, the bank's financial condition, rules and regulations, and the level of competition in the banking industry. These factors can affect investment risk in banking in different ways, such as affecting bank earnings, increasing or decreasing liquidity, or changing the way the bank generates income.

Investors must consider the determinants of investment risk in banking before deciding to invest in this sector, because the risks associated with banking can affect their investment results in the long term. Therefore, it is very important for investors to understand the determinants of investment risk in banking and consider these factors before making investment decisions.

There are 43 findings in this research topic, including: (1) non-financial performance (environmental, social, governance); (2) asset growth; (3) financial leverage; (4) liquidity; (5) Price Earning Ratio/PER; (6) inflation; (7) deposit interest; (8) currency exchange rates; (9) capital structure; (10) operating leverage, financial leverage; (11) abnormal returns; (12) expert system; (13) Bid-Ask Spread; (14) Cost of Equity Capital; (15) stock returns; (16) ownership structure; (17) acquisition; (18) Return On Assets/ROA; (19) Return On Equity/ROE; (20) active passive portfolio; (21) motivation; (22) knowledge; (23) Good Corporate Governance/GCG; (24) accounting information; (25) current ratio; (26) Debt to Asset Ratio/DAR; (27) Debt to Equity Ratio/DER; (28) Net Profit Margin/NPM; (29) Covid-19; (30) Bank Indonesia interest rates; (31) financial ratios; (32) macroeconomics; (33) microeconomics; (34) investment risk reserve; (35) company performance; (36) information technology; (37) religiosity; (38) digital assets; (39) cryptocurrencies; (40) Disclosure of Quality of Operating Segment/disclosure of operating segments; (41) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR; (42) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR; and (43) Non Performing Loans/NPL

Mapping Literature Review regarding the Influence of Investment Risk

The influence of investment risk on banking is the impact of the level of risk taken by banks in making investments. Investment risk in banking can come from various sources such as market price fluctuations, changes in interest rates, or global economic uncertainty. If the bank has a diversified investment portfolio and has acceptable risk, then the impact of investment risk can be controlled and profits from the investment can be obtained. However, if a bank makes too many investments with high risk, the bank can experience large losses and this can affect the bank's financial stability.

Therefore, it is important for banks to manage investment risks well and ensure that they have effective policies and procedures to measure and address investment risks. This will help banks to ensure that they have sufficient resources to maintain stability and earn profits from their investments.

There are several things that are influenced by investment risk in banking, including: (1) stock trading volume; (2) interest in investing; (3) investor response in making investment decisions; (4) financial performance; (5) underpricing; (6) stock returns; and (7) share price,

Mapping Literature Review regarding Investment Risk Management Methods

The Investment Risk Management Method is a process carried out by banks to identify, analyze and overcome potential risks related to investments made by banks. This aims to ensure that investments made by banks have a reasonable and acceptable level of risk and also ensure that banks have sufficient funds to overcome the risks associated with such investments.

There are several investment risk management methods, including: (1) the Options-based Risk Management/OBRiM framework method; (2) Value at Risk/VAR with the Variance Covariance approach; (3) Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity/ARCH & Generalized ARCH/GARCH; (4) Naïve Bayes algorithm; (5) Deep Learning/DL; (6) Data Mining; (7) Unified Modeling Language/UML for online systems; (8) Historical Back Simulation; (9) Risk Metrics; (10) Monte Carlo Simulation; (11) Conditionally Heteroscedastic Time Series Model;

(12) Generalized Pareto Distribution/GDP; (13) Generalized Extreme Value/GEV; (14) Expected Shortfall Expansion Cornish-Fisher; (15) Vector Error Correction Model/VECM; (16) Decision Usefulness; (17) Capital Asset Pricing Model/CAPM; (18) Value at Risk-Asymmetric Power Autoregressive/VaR-APARCH; (19) Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process/F-AHP; (20) Single Index Model; and (21) Treasury Dealing Room/TDR system; and (22) Risk-Return Analysis.

Mapping Literature Review around Problems in Investment Risk

There are several findings in this research topic, including:

First, the investment risk strategy for sharia mutual fund portfolios can include several things such as the following: (1) Portfolio diversification; (2) Analyzing investment instruments; (3) Reduce long-term risks; (4) Regular monitoring; and (5) Consult with professionals.

Second, mitigating investment risk by actualizing istislah reasoning, namely considering ethical and moral values in making investment decisions. In the actualization of istislah reasoning, investors evaluate the investment they will take by considering whether the investment is in accordance with the values they adhere to, such as justice, humanity, and a balance between the interests of individuals and society. By considering ethical and moral factors, investors can minimize investment risks related to controversy or unethical business practices. It also helps investors ensure that their investment decision making is in line with their beliefs and values, helping to increase confidence and consistency in long-term investing.

Third, the appropriateness of investment risk is determined by several factors, including: (1) Asset quality; (2) Capital adequacy; (3) Profitability; (4) Management quality; and (5) Regulation and supervision.

Fourth, investment risk sensitivity, which is a measure of how changes in a certain factor will affect the results or value of an investment. In terms of investment in banking, several factors can influence risk sensitivity, including: (1) Interest rates; (2) Economic conditions; (3) Asset quality; (4) Regulatory policies; and (5) Market conditions.

Fifth, cash waqf investment risk management, which is a process that helps waqf managers determine, monitor and minimize the risks associated with waqf investments. This process involves identifying risks, evaluating risks, creating action plans, and periodically monitoring and revising action plans. To manage cash waqf investment risks, waqf managers can take several actions such as portfolio diversification, selecting investment instruments with a risk level that suits the waqf's objectives and risk profile, as well as regularly monitoring and monitoring investment performance.

Sixth, the risk of investing in Hajj funds, namely that there are certain risks that potential investors need to pay attention to. Some risks that may occur include: (1) Market fluctuations; (2) Currency risk; (3) Management credibility risk; (4) Regulatory risk.

Seventh, the risk of investing in Dinar Coin/DNC. Here are some potential risks to consider before investing in Dinar Coin or other cryptocurrencies: (1) Price volatility; (2) Lack of regulation; (3) Security threats; and (4) Technical risks.

Eighth, digital pawnshop services, which can help simplify the investment process, but like other investments, risks still exist. Several risks that need to be considered when investing through Pegadaian's digital services include: (1) Security risks; (2) Risk of price fluctuation; (3) Regulatory risk; (4) Liquidity risk.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Investment Risk Mitigation

There are several findings in this research topic, including:

First, mitigate investment risk with income smoothing, namely: (1) Providing a buffer for difficult economic periods; (2) Improving the company's reputation; (3) Attract more investors. However, it is important to remember that income smoothing also has several risks, such as: public trust in the company will be disturbed and legal action will be required.

Second, risk mitigation with digital investment- based financial literacy can help minimize investment risk in several ways. Here are some of them: (1) Education about investment products; (2) Financial monitoring; (3) Portfolio diversification; (4) Recognize signs of fraud; and

(5) Risk management. However, although digital financial literacy helps in minimizing investment risks, there are still risks inherent in every investment product. Therefore, it is very important for investors to conduct due diligence and understand the risks associated with each product before deciding to invest.

Third, real asset investment risk mitigation is carried out in several ways, including: (1) Dividing investment into several types of real assets; (2) Study and understand the conditions of the property market, stock market and other markets in which you invest; (3) Before deciding to invest, make sure that you have carried out an in-depth project analysis; (4) Longer time periods usually provide an opportunity to ride out market fluctuations and provide better results in the end; (5) Working with professionals such as investment managers or financial consultants can help understand risks and make better investment decisions; and (6) After investing, be sure to monitor the investment regularly to ensure that you understand market changes and make adjustments if necessary.

Fourth, mitigate investment risk in financing:

- (1) Mudharabah, namely: determining the risk profile and return profile in accordance with the investor's risk tolerance, ensuring that the fund manager (Mudharib) has adequate ability and experience in managing funds, determining the appropriate investment period and ensuring that the period chosen is in accordance with the profile risks and expected returns, and ensuring that the fund manager has an adequate internal control system to monitor and manage investment risks.
- (2) Murabahah, namely: ensuring that the selling price determined is a fair market price, ensuring that the goods received by the customer are quality goods and meet the specified specifications, and determining the appropriate payment term and ensuring that the term chosen is in accordance with the profile risks and expected returns.
- (3) Ijarah, namely: ensuring that the rental property has a stable sales value and meets the specified quality standards, determining the appropriate rental period and ensuring that the selected period is in accordance with the risk profile and expected results, ensuring that the location of the rental property has attractiveness to prospective tenants, and ensuring that property owners have the experience and ability to manage rental properties.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding investment risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking during the period 1995 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 280 research articles.
- In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, research developments regarding investment risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking are divided into 16 clusters and 116 items. Cluster 1 consists of 39 items, cluster 2 consists of 12 items, cluster 3 consists of 11 items, cluster 4 consists of 10 items, cluster 5 consists of 10 items, cluster 6 consists of 8 items, cluster 7 consists of 8 items, cluster 8 consists of 7 items, cluster 9 consists of 6 items, cluster 10 consists of 6 items, cluster 11 consists of 6 items, cluster 12 consists of 5 items, cluster 13 consists of 4 items, cluster 14 consists of 4 items, cluster 15 consists of 3 items, and cluster 16 consists of 1 item.
- Based on a literature review, there are 9 main research themes surrounding investment risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: (1) Definition and objectives of risk management; (2) Risk monitoring; (3) Strategy, risk level, policies, procedures, limits; (4) Identification, measurement, monitoring, control, information systems; (5) Risk determinants; (6) Effect of risk; (7) Risk management methods; (8) Risk issues; and (9) Risk mitigation.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- The results of the e- review literature study can be explained in a more complex way.

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